

Research Article

MYHUSM Application

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Abstract: As we know, medical treatment is very important to human life because it can save thousands of lives. So, by having this, "HUSM" is a responsible place to provide medical treatments, medication and services for all of the people in Kota Bharu and nearby areas. Surely, there are many people who need to use the services from the hospital every day. So, the problem that occurs in the realm of "HUSM" involves the time that both patients and members of the public who want to see a doctor have to wait to perform the treatment. This is because some of us have experience when meeting with a specialist doctor where it takes a long time to wait up to one to two hours. With that, we feel that by taking the queue number early in the morning, we cannot solve the same problem. And with the system in place, it will be better and more effective. This is because having a system will make our lives easier, faster to complete their work and tasks efficiently. It is because the system works to support the daily work operations in the hospital that need help to perform their daily tasks correctly and efficiently.

Keywords: Medical treatment, patient, specialist doctors, queue number.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Hospital Universiti Sains Malaysia (HUSM), like many other hospitals in Malaysia, experiences significant inefficiencies in its patient registration and appointment scheduling processes. The current queuing system results in long wait times for patients and increased workload for hospital staff, negatively impacting the overall efficiency and effectiveness of hospital operations. Patients typically wait one to two hours in outpatient departments to register and make appointments, leading to frustration and potential delays in receiving medical care (Atherton et al., 2024). Additionally, hospital staff manually record appointments, causing patients to waste time on the phone and endure repetitive processes (Lee et al., 2020). This manual *approach* increases staff workload and introduces inefficiencies. Patients must physically visit the hospital to fill out registration forms and make doctor's appointments. This process is neither quick nor convenient, often requiring patients to wait for a date set by the hospital after registration. Locating and retrieving old patient information and records is time-consuming, contributing to delays and inefficiencies in patient care. Although some hospitals offer

online appointment services, patients still need to verify their appointment slip cards at the front desk before proceeding to the waiting room. This verification process extends outpatient wait times and diminishes service efficiency (Harun et al., 2024). A lack of sufficient medical staff exacerbates the long registration process, further increasing wait times and reducing the quality of patient care (Suk et al., 2021). Long wait times and inefficient processes lead to patient dissatisfaction, potentially impacting their health and overall experience at the hospital.

2. PROPOSED SYSTEMS – OBJECTIVES OF THE NEW SYSTEM

After we have studied and seen the problems that arise among us also with this current system, we have tried and figured out how to solve the problem. Therefore, we have proposed to create several systems involving queue numbers that are easier, faster and according to the patient's time into the system under HUSM. This is because, any patient who wants to see a doctor or get treatment just needs to open the website we designed and only enter the ID card number and telephone number to choose the time and day they want to see the doctor. This is the main reason why we chose to create the easiest website to create a treatment system with doctors, because it makes it easier for patients and staff to manage their affairs, and patients only need to come at the time they choose. Next, regarding this system we will create a pop reminder system to ensure patients do not forget what they have booked to see the doctor. However, for the staff, we no longer need to fill out forms one by one and no longer need to identify the patient's identification card which will take a long time. Not only that with this system, the staff only need to open the system to see the number of patients who want to come and how many will be present day by day depending on the number filled from time to time. So, with this new system, we believe it will make it easier for both parties to come to the hospital according to the time set by themselves.

3. SCOPE OF THE NEW SYSTEM

"MyHUSM" is a system that was established as a result of innovation from the existing workflow where it is able to some extent to help both parties in making the workflow more efficient and easier. In addition, in line with the problems in the existing workflow, which is that patients have to wait a very long time to get a turn to see a doctor, so with the existence of the "MyHUSM" system, it provides more benefits to patients by allowing them to make reservations online by choosing Date and time according to the time the patient wants but according to the availability of time. Not only that, but this system also has the advantage that the patient can press the set alert time to allow the user to give them a reminder according to the set time which the alarm will sound when there is enough time to remember. In addition, the patient will be accompanied by a number which the patient will have to show to the staff as proof of the online booking. In addition, at the same time, the system level has led to very significant changes in the scope of staff duties which make it more efficient and organized. This is because, they only need to open the website by entering their work email, check the number of patients from time to time and only need to click the approve button and random room only to allow patient data not to agree into the system. This clearly shows that staff no longer need to contact any party or provide patients with paper forms which slows down the process and is unprofessional.

4. SYSTEM BENEFITS/ SIGNIFICANT OF THE NEW SYSTEM

With the new systems that we provide I believe it can make it easier for all side of people which are patients, staff and also the doctor because the time to wait will be shorter. One more thing is the patient just needs to arrive at the hospital just 15 minutes earlier just to see the doctor because they can register it online.

4.1 Patient

Among the benefits that the patient get is being able to make things easier for them as we say earlier that the time of waiting will be cut and they don't need to come earlier to hospital to register and do a check-up. They just need to arrive at the hospital 15 minutes earlier and don't need to register physically. They just need to open the websites and put the identification number and also phone number to register the checkup. After filling the ic number and phone number they need to choose the date and time to see the doctor. After all, be settled. He just needs to come 25 minutes earlier and the patient will also get the notification when it is their turn.

4.1 Staff

For the staff side, this new system is able to save their time and also less their burden on doing the task. As all of you can see on Figure 2 it is such a complicated jobs to do and too much thing they need to do. So, with these systems that we build I'm pretty it will help a lot. The staff will have more time doing other staff and they will be no issues about understaff in hospital. After the patient register the detail true websites staff just need to transfer the data or print out the patient information and send t directly to the doctor.

Figure 1. Patient New Flowchart

Figure 2. Staff flowchart

5. RECOMMENDATION

Addressing the issue of patient no-shows in hospitals requires a comprehensive approach that targets various contributing factors such as appointment reminders, parking issues, and scheduling efficiency. One effective strategy is implementing automated reminder systems. Sending reminders via SMS and email a few days before and a few hours before the appointment can significantly reduce the number of missed appointments due to forgetfulness. Additionally, automated phone call reminders can be particularly helpful for elderly patients or those who are not as comfortable with technology. This approach directly tackles the problem identified by Milner et al. (2021), where 41.8% of patients missed their appointments because they forgot about them. Improving scheduling efficiency is another crucial step. Reducing the indirect waiting time, the period between requesting and receiving an appointment, can be achieved by using advanced scheduling software that optimizes available time slots based on urgency and patient availability. Offering flexible scheduling options, such as evening and weekend appointments, can also accommodate patients' varying schedules, thereby reducing the likelihood of no-shows due to conflicts with work or other commitments. Parking difficulties also contribute significantly to patient no-shows and tardiness. Providing real-time updates on available parking spaces through a mobile app or website can help alleviate the stress and delays associated with finding a parking spot. Additionally, introducing shuttle services from nearby parking lots or offering valet parking can significantly reduce the burden of parking for patients. These measures address the issue highlighted by the Ministry of Health Malaysia, which reported a substantial demand for parking spaces at hospitals. Acknowledgments: In this section, you can acknowledge any support given to the project.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In summary, the redesign of our appointment process signifies a significant step towards a more effective and patient-centered healthcare encounter. To keep up with the rapidly changing world

of digital solutions, the antiquated and laborious method of making doctor appointments has been completely overhauled. Our consistent commitment to improving our patients' quality of life has propelled this development. Realizing how complicated and ineffective the old method was led to the decision to completely redesign the current configuration. We set out to streamline this procedure, and thank God, the results have gone beyond our expectations. Our team's meticulous creation and development of an online platform has brought in a new era of ease and accessibility for both staff and patients. The user-friendly nature of our website empowers patients with newfound capabilities, enabling them to effortlessly schedule appointments with their healthcare providers. This digital transition not only streamlines the appointment process but also promises a more seamless healthcare journey for everyone involved. The safety and security protocols implemented in our system underscore our commitment to safeguarding patient information, instilling confidence in users as they navigate our platform.

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